

The Employee's opinion on HR practices. A bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

The objective of a bibliometric examination paper is to inspect the verifiable worth of the distribution on a specific issue, which as of now talks about underneath it. The finding is additionally delineating the significance of the specific talked about issue that the ongoing methodology of HRM and SHRM will inspect. The VOS-viewer is useful to look at the profound detail of distributed articles. Over 80,000 distributed papers are accessible about HRM and more than 40,000 papers from 2012 on the setting of SHRM are there. This study gives data to specialists intrigued by the field of hierarchical citizenship conduct by giving an outline of patterns in the most famous catchphrases, diaries, and writers of articles examining the subject, which has become a seriously well-known topic lately. There is probability to dig further into this subject.

Keywords: Strategic Human Resource, Employee perception of HR practices, Theoretical perspective

Introduction

In this study, we explore the strategic human resource management (SHRM) field through the lens of the SHRM cycle model developed by Cao, Zhao, Chen, & Lv (2023). This model maps the journey of HR strategies and practices, starting from their creation to implementation, and how they are perceived by various stakeholders to achieve effective execution. A pivotal aspect of this model, as highlighted by Baumann & Marcum (2023), is the emphasis on the potential discrepancies among intended HR practices.

Recent research, including that of Song, Guo, Fu, Cooke, & Chen (2023), and Baumann & Marcum (2023), has increasingly focused on the employee's role in evaluating these dynamics. For instance, as de Beijer et al. (2022) noted, recent studies have seen a growing emphasis on employee perceptions of HR practices, particularly in their role in mediating the relationship between HRM and performance. Mir et al. (2022) and others have developed various theoretical models to explore these perceptions, underscoring the crucial impact of how employees perceive human resource practices, as opposed to management-implemented HR strategies, on employee behavior.

As the field of SHRM continues to grow, it confronts the task of integrating the expanding body of research on employee perspectives of HR practices. Historically, SHRM literature has explored these perspectives through a variety of theoretical lenses, leading to the development of diverse

models that categorize employee perception of HRM as either a precursor, mediator, or outcome, as noted by Campagna et al. (2023). Despite these advancements, there remains an ambiguity in how employee perceptions are conceptualized, a disparity that hinders a clear understanding of their correlation with actual HR practices and outcomes (Campagna et al., 2023).

This research is committed to conducting a comprehensive analysis of how employee perceptions of HRM are integrated within the realm of SHRM research. Its primary goal is to clarify the roles these perceptions play as antecedents, mediators, or outcomes within the field. We aim to gather and clarify the principal theoretical frameworks that form the foundation of the employee perspective in SHRM scholarship. Additionally, this study will undertake a critical examination of the methodologies used in empirical research to conceptualize and implement the understanding of HR practices from the viewpoint of employees. Through this detailed analysis, our intention is to establish a groundwork for future research avenues. These will aim to enhance the comprehension of the actual impact of HRM practices on both employee experiences and overall organizational results.

Our review builds upon and extends recent studies, such as those by Campagna et al. (2023) and Beijer & Züchner (2022). While Beijer & Züchner (2022) provided an analysis of the employee perceptions of Human Resource practices, our study expands this by also examining how these perceptions function within SHRM research, including their role as precursors, mediators, or outcomes. We also integrate and categorize literature on the conceptualizations of employee perspectives, the theoretical frameworks employed, and how these constructs are measured. Based on this comprehensive review.

In summary, this study offers a detailed exploration of employee perspectives on Human Resource Management, drawing from the S.HRM cycle model (Baumann & Marcum, 2023). We discuss how these perspectives are conceptualized in existing literature, examine the theoretical frameworks underpinning these concepts, and present a synthesis of empirical research findings. Our final goal is to provide actionable recommendations for future research.

Employee Impression of HRM as a Predecessor, Mediator, or Result:

Nishii and Wright (2008) developed the SHRM cycle framework, later expanded by Zheng et al. (2022), to analyze the intricate link between human resource management (HRM) and organizational performance. This model introduces the concept of 'variety' in HR practices, categorizing them into three types: intended HR practices as designed by the organization, actual HR practices executed by line managers, and the HR practices as experienced and perceived by employees, a notion further clarified by Hewett & Shantz (2022). At the heart of this framework is the recognition that there can be a significant disparity between what employees perceive as HR practices and what is actually implemented by line management. The SHRM cycle framework identifies these perceptions as playing three pivotal roles: as precursors, mediators, or outcomes. In their role as precursors, employees' perceptions of HRM are viewed as indicators that forecast their reactions, thereby molding their attitudes and behaviors, a point underscored by Jia et al. (2023).

This facet of the model recognizes the significant impact of employees' perceptions of HR practices on their workplace behavior. As mediators, the SHRM cycle framework posits that the gap between the HR practices implemented by management and those perceived by employees plays a crucial role. It suggests that employees' perceptions serve as an intermediary in the dynamic between HR practices applied by management and the resultant employee attitudes and behaviors, a concept underscored by Hewett & Shantz (2022). Furthermore, the framework considers employees' perceptions of HRM as potential outcome variables, shaped by the actual HR practices in place. This viewpoint underscores that the genuine HR practices enacted by an organization ultimately influence employees' perceptions of HRM.

In essence, the SHRM cycle framework, as proposed by Nishii and Wright and further explored by later researchers, offers a comprehensive understanding of the role of employee perceptions in HRM. It highlights that these perceptions can function as precursors, intermediaries, or outcomes in the nexus between HRM practices and organizational performance, illustrating the intricate interaction between managerial strategies and employee reactions.

Theoretical perspectives that explain the employee perspective on HRM:

There are three distinct types based on their focus. The initial group of theoretical frameworks focuses on the reciprocal interaction between individuals and organizations. As elaborated by Mahajan et al. (2022), these frameworks are grounded in the idea that organizations offer specific 'gestures' or HR practices to their employees. The emphasis here is on how employees perceive and respond to these organizational gestures. It posits that employees' perceptions of SHRM practices influence their contributions to the organization. This perspective views the employee-organization interaction as a reciprocal exchange where both parties offer and receive benefits.

The second set of theoretical perspectives highlights the nature of communication between organizations and their employees. These perspectives focus on a more organizationally driven approach, emphasizing how organizations communicate with and engage their employees. This category of perspectives underscores the importance of effective communication strategies in the implementation and perception of HR practices, reflecting a top-down approach from the organization to its employees.

The third category, as outlined by Liu et al. (2022), centers on understanding employee well-being through the lens of occupational health psychology. This approach examines the impact of HR practices on individual well-being, offering insights into the direct and indirect effects of HRM on employee health and wellness. It emphasizes the significance of HR practices in shaping not just organizational outcomes but also the personal well-being of employees.

In summary, these three categories of theoretical perspectives provide a comprehensive framework for understanding the expert view on HRM.

Theoretical perspectives from an exchange relationship perspective:

A key concept related to SET is the psychological contract, which represents the unspoken beliefs, expectations, and informal obligations between an employer and employee (Van den Groenendaal, Freese, Poell, & Kooij, 2023). This contract is characterized by mutual, albeit often unarticulated, expectations between the two parties and encompasses the scope of duties and responsibilities. The psychological contract also addresses whether these mutually agreed upon duties and responsibilities are being met (Kellner, Townsend, Loudoun, & Wilkinson, 2023).

Closely related to the notion of SET and psychological contracts is the Equity Theory (April, Dharani, & April, 2023). This theory is used to assess perceptions of fairness, focusing less on the actual outcomes and more on the perceived equity of these outcomes (Lepak, Hansen, Hooten, Brauch, & Vigil, 2022). To determine perceived fairness, one examines the ratio of inputs and outputs, which provides the employee with a sense of consistency or disparity (Lepak et al., 2022).

Additionally, the (P-E) fit theory, as discussed by Bohndick, Breetzke, and Rosman (2022), focuses on the alignment between individual characteristics and elements of their environment. Individual traits include personal needs, values, and goals, while environmental aspects encompass both extrinsic and intrinsic rewards, job demands, and social factors (Bohdick et al., 2022).

Theoretical perspectives from an occupational health perspective:

The third set of theoretical approaches emphasizes comprehending employee well-being. This perspective integrates insights from the Demand-Control Model (D-CM) (Vosko, Basok, Spring, Candiz, & George, 2022) and the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, as investigated by HR scholars Parent-Lamarche, Dextras-Gauthier, & Julien (2023). These models scrutinize HR practices in the context of job demands and resources. Job demands, such as intense workload and emotional pressures, are typically associated with reduced employee well-being (Bakker, Hetland, Olsen, & Espevik, 2022). On the other hand, job resources are elements of the job that aid in achieving work objectives and can alleviate the negative impact of job demands on well-being (Bakker et al., 2022). These resources can exist at different levels, including organizational (e.g., managerial support), social (e.g., colleague support), job-specific (e.g., clarity of job roles), and task-related (e.g., autonomy in work tasks) (Bakker et al., 2022).

Aligned with the D-CM and JD-R models, the Conservation of Resources (COR) theory emphasizes the acquisition, preservation, and defense of resources. This theory posits that individuals strive to retain and gain new resources, as resource loss can lead to heightened stress (Teng & Lou, 2022). Huo & Jiang (2023) define resources as "objects, personal characteristics, conditions, or energies valued by individuals," encompassing various job resources like social, personal, material, or emotional assets, including HR practices (Huo & Jiang, 2023). Within the JD-R model and COR theory, HR practices can be perceived by employees as either demands or resources. This perception significantly shapes their effect on employee well-being (Laiho, Saru, & Seeck, 2022). Consequently, HR practices, based on their execution and perception, can potentially lead to adverse effects on employee well-being (Jiang et al., 2022). This highlights the crucial need for understanding and effectively managing HR practices to ensure they are perceived as supportive resources rather than burdensome demands, thereby positively contributing to employee well-being.

Descriptive Versus Evaluative Conceptualizations of Employee Perceptions of HRM:

Within the field of employee perceptions of HR practices, a significant variation exists in the nature and focus of these perceptions. Specifically, there's considerable diversity in how employee perceptions of HR practices are conceptualized and quantified across different studies (Bruinhof, Vacaru, van den Heuvel, de Weerth, & Beijers, 2022). For example, certain research endeavors delve into employees' perceived availability of HR practices, centering on the HR practices that employees are exposed to in their work environment (Den Hartog & Asakura, 2022). Other studies delve into employees' satisfaction with HR practices (Ryou, Tay, Ossa, & Arola, 2023), the intensity of HR practices (Ryou et al., 2023), or their effectiveness. Research indicates "a considerable variation in levels of perceived HR practices, coupled with a lack of clarity in how these practices are commonly reported in existing studies" (Kühn et al., 2023).

Scope:

An extensive literature review was undertaken to examine the empirical research on the relationship between perceived HRM and its outcomes, focusing on studies published between 2000 and May 2019. This research spanned 11 internationally recognized peer-reviewed journals in the fields of HRM, applied psychology, and management, including notable publications like

the Academy of Management Journal and Human Resource Management. The year 2000 marked the beginning of the review period, reflecting a growing interest in the study of employee perceptions of HR practices around this time.

To be included in the review, studies needed to meet several criteria. They had to examine multiple HR practices, reflecting the belief that a system of HR practices has a more significant impact than individual practices. This review emphasized studies that looked at employee perceptions across various HR practices, avoiding those that focused on single practices. These practices encompassed aspects like training, performance management, and employee participation. Additionally, included studies were required to either use a specific scale for measuring employee perception of HR practices or fully present the scale used. Theoretical framing of employee perception of HRM was also a necessity. The review concentrated on the item content related to HR practices rather than the overall HRM system evaluation, following the reasoning that employees are better positioned to report on their experiences at the practice level. Finally, the primary focus of the selected studies had to be on employee perception of HR practices, excluding studies where this was a moderating variable.

Description of literature:

The majority of the selected studies were published in HR-focused journals, “such as the International Journal of Human Resource Management (17), Human Resource Management Journal (10), and Human Resource Management (6). Additional publications appeared in the Journal of Management (4), Journal of Applied Psychology (3), Personnel Review (2), Human Relations (1), Journal of Management Studies (1), and Academy of Management Journal (1). Regarding research design, 35 studies were cross-sectional, nine were longitudinal, and one combined both approaches. Qualitative research was excluded, mainly because the specific research questions were not addressed in these studies. Most studies (38) examined HR practices as a HRM index (e.g., high-commitment or high-performance HR bundles), while seven studies focused on individual HR practices”.

Results:

The outcomes are analyzed based on various aspects such as conceptualization of employee perceptions, theoretical frameworks used, and operationalization methods.

In a comprehensive review of empirical studies on employee perceptions of HRM, three key themes emerged. First, the majority of studies (34 in total) considered employee perceptions as a precursor, primarily exploring their effects on performance outcomes at individual or organizational levels (53%), with some focusing on employee well-being. Ten studies examined these perceptions as mediators, particularly between management-rated HRM and various outcomes, while three treated them as consequences, investigating different antecedents. Second, the studies utilized diverse theoretical frameworks to understand employee perceptions of HR practices. The SHRM process framework was predominant, featured in over half of the studies. Other notable theories included social exchange, social information processing, HRM system strength, HR attributions, work demands-resources model, job demand-control model, the theory of reasoned action, and HR differentiation. Lastly, the studies presented a combination of

descriptive and evaluative conceptualizations of employee perceptions of HRM. Descriptive items like participation opportunities were common, alongside evaluative assessments focusing on HR practice effectiveness, fairness, and satisfaction.

Methodology

This study conducts a bibliometric analysis on the aforementioned literature, highlighting the significance of HRM and SHRM. The data utilized in this study were extracted from Dimension.ai. The search for published articles on HRM and SHRM primarily spanned from 2007 to 2023, with ongoing research. A total of 95,000 publications were identified on SHRM issues, and 120,056 on HRM. From these, 70,750 articles were selected for detailed examination. The VOS-viewer tool was employed for in-depth analysis.

According to Rosado-Cubero, Hernández, Jiménez, & Freire-Rubio (2023), bibliometric studies facilitate the exploration, organization, and analysis of large data sets, enabling insights into past trends and predicting future developments in research. Bibliometric analysis has been extensively applied in various disciplines, including strategic human resource management and leadership (Stone & Patterson, 2023). A comprehensive review of references revealed that topics on strategic human resource and human resource management appeared across multiple fields, including social cognitive sciences, medicine and health sciences, human society studies, commerce, management, tourism, and education. This analysis helps in understanding the evolution of the human resource management debate over the last two decades, identifying key trends and developments in the field. The VOS-viewer science mapping software was utilized for this purpose.

Criteria for choosing

NO.	STEPS	LOCATORS
1.	All available search with word of HRM or SHRM	70,750
2.	Publication restrictions	95,000

For examination the bibliometric networks, we supposed to use partial counted method and also for analyzing references with these methods:

- Historical evolution.
- Single and Co-citation analysis.
- Single and Co-authorship analysis.

Analysis with key steps: Growth rate of Human Resource management using data analytics

Trend analysis with publication in year on Human Resource Management and Strategic Human Resource

Trend analysis according to published papers in different Journals.

Trend analysis according to published papers in different Journals.

Trend analysis according to frequent terms.

Trend analysis according to Researcher network.

Trend analysis according to countries contributions.

Trend analysis according to network analysis of keywords.

References

1. Akingbola, K., Kerekou, S., & Tohon, A. (2023). Employee engagement in non-profit organizations: the role of perception of HR and organizational culture. *Journal of Management Development*.
2. April, K., Dharani, B., & April, A. (2023). *Lived Experiences of Exclusion in the Workplace: Psychological & Behavioural Effects*: Emerald Publishing Limited.
3. Bakker, A. B., Hetland, J., Olsen, O. K., & Espevik, R. (2022). Daily transformational leadership: A source of inspiration for follower performance? *European Management Journal*.
4. Baumann, H. M., & Marcum, T. M. (2023). Human capital and legal perspectives on remote work: recommendations for organizations. *Management Research Review*.
5. Beijer, D., & Züchner, S. L. (2022). Commentary: SPTBN5, encoding the β V-spectrin protein, leads to a syndrome of intellectual disability, developmental delay, and seizures. *Frontiers in Molecular Neuroscience*, 15, 1011856.
6. Bohndick, C., Breetzke, J., & Rosman, T. (2022). A comparison between different ways to assess demands-abilities fit in higher education: Empirical results and recommendations for research practice. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 896710.
7. Bruinhof, N., Vacaru, S. V., van den Heuvel, M. I., de Weerth, C., & Beijers, R. (2022). Prenatal hair cortisol concentrations during the COVID-19 outbreak: Associations with maternal psychological stress and infant temperament. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 144, 105863.
8. Campagna, A. X., Desmarais, E. D., French, B., Underwood, J. J., Majdandžić, M., Beijers, R., . . . Ahmetoglu, E. (2023). Temperament and behaviour problems in children: A multilevel analysis of cross-cultural differences. *Infant and Child Development*, e2443.
9. Cao, M., Zhao, S., Chen, J., & Lv, H. (2023). Employees' HR attributions count: the effects of high-performance work systems on employees' thriving at work and emotional exhaustion. *Personnel Review*.
10. Chourasia, A., Bahuguna, P., & Raju, T. B. (2023). Strategic Human Resource Management, a Road to Organizational Performance: Evidence from Public Sector Organizations in the Oil and Gas Sector. *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*, 12(First Special Issue 2023), 66-90.

11. de Beijer, M. T., Bezstarosti, K., Luijten, R., Doff, W. A., Boor, P. P., Pieterman, R. F., . . . Doukas, M. (2022). Immunopeptidome of hepatocytes isolated from patients with HBV infection and hepatocellular carcinoma. *JHEP Reports*, 4(11), 100576.
12. Den Hartog, L., & Asakura, A. (2022). Implications of notch signaling in duchenne muscular dystrophy. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 13, 984373.
13. Dineen, B. R., Yu, K. Y. T., & Stevenson-Street, J. (2023). Recruitment in personnel psychology and beyond: Where we've been working, and where we might work next. *Personnel Psychology*.
14. Hewett, R., & Shantz, A. (2022). 7. The role of line managers in the formation of employees' HR attributions. *Research Handbook on Line Managers*, 95.
15. Huo, M.-L., & Jiang, Z. (2023). Work–life conflict and job performance: The mediating role of employee wellbeing and the moderating role of trait extraversion. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 205, 112109.
16. Jia, J., Zhao, T., Liu, Z., Liang, Y., Li, F., Li, Y., . . . Zhou, C. (2023). Association between healthy lifestyle and memory decline in older adults: 10 year, population based, prospective cohort study. *bmj*, 380.
17. Jiang, C., Sun, J., Li, R., Yan, S., Chen, W., Guo, L., . . . Huang, W. (2022). A reactive oxygen species burst causes haploid induction in maize. *Molecular Plant*, 15(6), 943-955.
18. Kellner, A., Townsend, K., Loudoun, R., & Wilkinson, A. (2023). High reliability Human Resource Management (HRM): A system for high risk workplaces. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 33(1), 170-186.
19. Kühn, S., Schmalen, K., Beijers, R., Tyborowska, A., Roelofs, K., & Weerth, C. d. (2023). Green Is Not the Same as Green: Differentiating Between the Association of Trees and Open Green Spaces With Children's Brain Structure in the Netherlands. *Environment and Behavior*, 00139165231183095.
20. Laiho, M., Saru, E., & Seeck, H. (2022). "It's the work climate that keeps me here": the interplay between the HRM process and emergent factors in the construction of employee experiences. *Personnel review*, 51(2), 444-463.
21. Lepak, J. M., Hansen, A. G., Hooten, M. B., Brauch, D., & Vigil, E. M. (2022). Rapid proliferation of the parasitic copepod, *Salmincola californiensis* (Dana), on kokanee salmon, *Oncorhynchus nerka* (Walbaum), in a large Colorado reservoir. *Journal of Fish Diseases*, 45(1), 89-98.
22. Liu, C., He, Q., Song, D., Jackson, J., Faria, A. F., Jiang, X., . . . Sun, Z. (2022). Electroless deposition of copper nanoparticles integrates polydopamine coating on reverse osmosis membranes for efficient biofouling mitigation. *Water Research*, 217, 118375.
23. Mahajan, A., Spracklen, C. N., Zhang, W., Ng, M. C., Petty, L. E., Kitajima, H., . . . Kim, Y. J. (2022). Multi-ancestry genetic study of type 2 diabetes highlights the power of diverse populations for discovery and translation. *Nature genetics*, 54(5), 560-572.
24. Mahmood, M., Ostrovskiy, A., & Capar, N. (2023). Effect of orientation training on employee and firm performance. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, 42(4), 49-62.
25. Mir, W. J., Alamoudi, A., Yin, J., Yorov, K. E., Maity, P., Naphade, R., . . . Nematulloev, S. (2022). Lecithin capping ligands enable ultrastable perovskite-phase CsPbI₃ quantum dots for Rec. 2020 bright-red light-emitting diodes. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 144(29), 13302-13310.
26. Parent-Lamarque, A., Dextras-Gauthier, J., & Julien, A.-S. (2023). Toward a new model of human resource management practices: construction and validation of the High Wellbeing and Performance Work System Scale. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1151781.
27. Rosado-Cubero, A., Hernández, A., Jiménez, F. J. B., & Freire-Rubio, T. (2023). Promotion of entrepreneurship through business incubators: Regional analysis in Spain. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 190, 122419.
28. Ryou, H., Tay, F. R., Ossa, A., & Arola, D. (2023). Preparation of collagen fibrils from mineralized tissues and evaluation by atomic force microscopy. *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical*

- Materials, 138, 105624.
29. Shahzad, K., Hong, Y., Jiang, Y., & Niaz, H. (2022). Knowledge-Intensive HRM systems and performance of knowledge-intensive teams: Mediating role of team knowledge processes. *Group & Organization Management*, 10596011211063667.
 30. Shanafelt, T. D., West, C. P., Sinsky, C., Trockel, M., Tutty, M., Wang, H., . . . Dyrbye, L. N. (2022). Changes in burnout and satisfaction with work-life integration in physicians and the general US working population between 2011 and 2020. Paper presented at the Mayo Clinic Proceedings.
 31. Song, Q., Guo, P., Fu, R., Cooke, F. L., & Chen, Y. (2023). Does human resource system strength help employees act proactively? The roles of crisis strength and work engagement. *Human Resource Management*, 62(2), 213-228.
 32. Stone, A. G., & Patterson, K. (2023). The history of leadership focus. Springer Books, 689-715.
 33. Teng, E., & Lou, M. (2022). Trickle-Down Effect of Supervisor's Job Insecurity: Moderating Role of Supervisor's Goal Striving. Paper presented at the Academy of Management Proceedings.
 34. Van den Groenendaal, S. M. E., Freese, C., Poell, R. F., & Kooij, D. T. (2023). Inclusive human resource management in freelancers' employment relationships: The role of organizational needs and freelancers' psychological contracts. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 33(1), 224-240.
 35. van Dijk, J., Flerlage, H., Beijer, S., Slootweg, J. C., & van Wezel, A. P. (2022). Safe and sustainable by design: A computer-based approach to redesign chemicals for reduced environmental hazards. *Chemosphere*, 296, 134050.
 36. Vosko, L. F., Basok, T., Spring, C., Candiz, G., & George, G. (2022). COVID-19 among migrant farmworkers in Canada: Employment strain in a transnational context: ILO Working Paper.
 37. Zheng, Y., Oguzlu, H., Baldelli, A., Zhu, Y., Song, M., Pratap-Singh, A., & Jiang, F. (2022). Sprayable cellulose nanofibrils stabilized phase change material Pickering emulsion for spray coating application. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 291, 119583.